

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

Value Added Course 2020-21 academic year for MPT

YOGA

**SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY
COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY**

Value Added course
on
YOGA
for MPT 2019 batch

Course duration
10 weeks (40 hours)

Course Objectives

1. To provide the necessary knowledge of practice of yoga so that the students learn to practice and also to teach yoga to all age groups for promoting their health and effectiveness.
2. To provide the necessary knowledge and skills of performing Asanas, Mudras, Bandas, Pranayama and meditative postures.

Made with PosterMyWall.com www.srinivasuniversity.edu.in

Course period	From November 2020 till January 2021, during 3 rd semester (10 weeks)
Duration	40 hours (4 hours/week)
Language of instruction	English
Participants	MPT 2 nd year postgraduates (2019 batch)

Course Objectives:

1. To provide the necessary knowledge of the theory and practice of yoga so that the

students learn to practice and also to teach yoga to all age groups for promoting their health and effectiveness.

- To provide the necessary knowledge of Asanas, Mudras, Bandas, Pranayama and meditative postures.

COURSE OUTLINE		
MODULE	TOPIC	HOURS
1	Introduction: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yoga philosophy, origin of Yoga, principles and importance of yoga. Basic yogic principles: Stages of yoga. Types of yoga: Hatha Yoga, Raja Yoga, Laya Yoga, Bhakti Yoga, Ashtanga Yoga, Karma Yoga. 	3
2	Effects of yoga on various systems: Musculoskeletal, Neuro, Cardiovascular, metabolic, Gastrointestinal, mental and reproductive systems.	4
3	Yoga Asana: Principles, muscle work and kinematics; Relevance of asana to exercise. Types of asana: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Forward Bending Asanas: Uttanasana, Padahastanasana, Prasarirapaduttanasana, Janusirsasana, Triangamukhiekapadapaschimottanasana, Paschimottanasana, Ardhapadmabaddapaschimottanasana. Back Bending Asanas: Salabhasana, Bhujangasana, Ustrasana, Dhanurasana, Urdhavadhanurasana, Chakrasana. Standing Asanas: Suryanamaskar, Utkatasana, Urdhvhastanasana, Urdhvhadhanguliasana, Prasarirapadahastanasana, Trikonasana, Parsavakonasana, Ardachandrasana, Adhomukhasavanasana, Veerabhadrasana. Inversions: Sirsasana, Sarvangasana, Halasana. Twisting Asanas: Floor twisting, Chair twisting, Standing twisting. Sitting Asanas: Sukhasana, Bhaddakonasana, Padmasana, Ardhapadmasana, Veerasana, Dandasana, Upavistakonasana. Supine Asanas: Suptapadangustasana, Sukhsamvyayamas. Restorative Asanas: Suptaveerasana, Suptabhaddakonasana, Setubandhasarvangasana, Savasana Tratakas: Visual Training Asanas 	25
4	Pranayama, Bandhas and Mudras: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pranayama definition, phases, types and principles (Ujjai Pranayama, Anulomvilom, Bhastrika, Bhrumri, Nadishodhan, Kapalbharti, Omkar, Suryabhedana, Chandrabhedana). Difference between pranayama and deep breathing. Meaning of Bandhas and mudras, physical effects, types. 	5
5	Dhyana: Meaning and benefits of Dhyana; Intellectual concentration vs dhyana.	3

References:

- Sri G Dayanidi & Smt. Reena Dayanidy. Principles and methods of yoga practices. ICYER.
- Horovitz E. G. Yoga Therapy: Theory and Practice. 1st ed. Routledge, 2015.

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This is to certify that

AJANYA N K (5SU19PT801)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from November 2020 to January 2021

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
Assistant Professor
Course Instructor

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean
College of Physiotherapy

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This is to certify that

HARSH NAINWANI (5SU19PT802)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from November 2020 to January 2021

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
Assistant Professor
Course Instructor

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean
College of Physiotherapy

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This is to certify that

MAGHNA E (5SU19PT803)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from November 2020 to January 2021

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
Assistant Professor
Course Instructor

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean
College of Physiotherapy

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This is to certify that

RIYA NAINWANI (5SU19PT804)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from November 2020 to January 2021

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
Assistant Professor
Course Instructor

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean
College of Physiotherapy

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF PHYSIOTHERAPY

CERTIFICATE OF PARTICIPATION

This is to certify that

VARSHA K (5SU19PT805)

has successfully completed this 10 week value added course on
"Yoga" conducted from November 2020 to January 2021

Total Hours- 40

Dr. Radhika Gopal S
Assistant Professor
Course Instructor

Dr. S. Rajasekar
Dean
College of Physiotherapy